

THE EU-SEAKNOT PROJECT: ON THE WAY TO SETTLE A ROADMAP FOR SEVERE ACCIDENT RESEARCH

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Abstract

Severe Accidents (SAs) are known to dominate the risk associated to the commercial production of nuclear energy. A vast amount of research has been done for decades to practically eliminate potential large early radiological releases of fission products. At present, the existing research capabilities to optimize management of these events are being jeopardized by: the loss of knowledge and know-how due to seniors retirement; the lack of access to old archives containing **mostly legacy** experimental data; and, no less relevant, the reduction of human and technological resources. At the same time, new approaches for the SA assessment are being explored (Uncertainties and Sensitivity Analysis – UaSA, as in the [EURATOM H-2020 MUSA](#) project).

This paper introduces the **so-called** SEAKNOT project (SEvere Accident research and KNOWledge management for LWRs), launched under the frame of [EURATOM](#) Horizon Europe in October 2022. Coordinated by CIEMAT and participated by 17 organizations, the project is building a roadmap to effectively address the near- and mid-term needs in the field of SA to enable nuclear technology to keep and **further enhance** ~~increase~~ its current level of safety while accommodating forthcoming technological changes (WC-SMRs and near-term ATFs). To do so a critical assessment of the current state-of-the-art is being done based on a Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT), a **directory** of the validation data base and a Europe **wide** mapping of experimental infrastructures. The project gives an outstanding relevance to the knowledge and knowhow transfer to **young** ~~these~~ generations who will be responsible for conducting the necessary research in the coming decades, and activities like the Severe Accident Phenomenology course (SAP) and the European Review Meeting on Severe Accident Research (ERMSAR) are in the project portfolio for dissemination and communication activities.

Besides shortly **describing** the SEAKNOT project, the presentation will outline the progress made one year after its start.

PALABRAS CLAVE: SEVERE ACCIDENT ROADMAP; PIRT; SAP; ERMSAR.

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